

INVESTIGATION OF MIDDLE SCHOOL MATHEMATICS TEACHERS' INFORMAL STATISTICAL INFERENCE SKILLS AND STATISTICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine middle school mathematics teachers' Informal Statistical Inference (ISI) skills and the relationship between these skills and Statistical Content Knowledge (SCK). This research, which is based on the importance placed on statistical reasoning in the mathematics curriculum updated in Turkey in 2024, employs a qualitative case study design. The study group comprised 48 middle school mathematics teachers from different schools in the province of Mersin, Turkey. Data were collected using a three-component theoretical framework developed by Makar and Rubin (2009) (evidence from data, generalisation beyond data, and probabilistic language) and supported by expert opinion. The research results show that although the majority of teachers are successful in using concrete evidence in their inferences, they experience significant difficulties, particularly in the use of 'probabilistic language'. Furthermore, it was found that there is not always a linear relationship between teachers' SCK levels and their ISI skills; even some teachers with high domain knowledge used language that conveyed certainty in situations involving uncertainty. These findings highlight the necessity of pedagogical approaches that prioritise inferential reasoning over procedural knowledge in in-service training to ensure the success of the new curriculum.

Keywords: Middle school mathematics teachers, statistical inference, statistics content knowledge, informal statistical inference.

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st-century information society, individuals are expected to possess not only numerical skills but also the ability to critically examine data and make inferential judgments based on that data (Gaise II, 2020). This expectation, as stated by Wild and Pfannkuch (1999), requires a paradigm shift in statistics education away from traditional procedural and formula-based approaches toward a focus on conceptual understanding and data literacy. The concept of informal statistical inference (ISI) forms the basis of this change. Makar and Rubin (2009) state that the fundamental starting point for this change was the Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) movement, an approach described in Tukey's 1977 work as "looking at data to see what it seems to say."

ISI is the process of making logical generalisations from evidence obtained from observed sample data, rather than using formal statistical procedures (such as p-values and hypothesis tests) to conclude unknown population parameters from observed samples (Zieffler et al., 2008). ISI is a fundamental mechanism that enables students not only to understand statistical processes but also to think deeply about and understand fundamental concepts such as variability and uncertainty. Zieffler et al. (2008) emphasised that variability lies at the heart of statistical thinking, noting that this concept is insufficiently addressed and that this constitutes a fundamental deficiency in students' statistical reasoning. They stated that ISI is a critical approach for understanding this variability and coping with uncertainty. Makar and Rubin (2009) stated that ISI provides students with the opportunity to draw their own inferences

in statistical situations involving uncertainty and variability, thereby fostering a deeper understanding of these concepts.

ISI has become a conceptual centre in the literature on statistical education over the past twenty years and has evolved into a dynamic field of research. This dynamism has ensured the continuous development of the theoretical frameworks that define ISI. ISI, whose foundations were laid by approaches that situated inferential reasoning within broad frameworks, such as Wild and Pfannkuch's (1999) statistical thinking cycle, has since been deepened by more specific, operational models. With Ben-Zvi and Garfield (2004) hierarchically defining the goals of statistical education, ISI became clearly established as a critical skill at the level of statistical reasoning, distinct from formal procedures, and was first systematically defined by Zieffler et al. (2008) within a three-component framework. Subsequently, Makar and Rubin (2009) provided a three-component framework for ISI (Generalisation Beyond Data, Evidence from Data, Probabilistic Language), which has become a powerful and applicable analytical tool for researchers. This development process has transformed ISI from merely a measure of student competence into a multidimensional and examinable structure centred on conceptual understanding, managing variability, and expressing uncertainty in statistics education. This study will also utilise the three-component ISI framework presented by Makar and Rubin (2009).

Table 1

Development of ISI

Year	Scientists	Focus Point	Basic Contribution
1999	Wild and Pfannkuch	It aims to explain the various dimensions of “statistical thinking” and how this way of thinking can be developed. It emphasizes that statistical thinking is not limited to data analysis, but also encompasses understanding variability, investigating causes, and model building processes. In this context, it is argued that statistical thinking is a multidimensional and complex process.	They have positioned inference as the final stage of the general thinking process.
2004	Ben-Zvi and Garfield	The focus is on the goals of statistics education. That is, the aim is to clarify the conceptual distinction between statistical literacy, reasoning, and thinking, to examine students' development in these areas, and to improve statistics education by sharing this information with educators.	They have placed ISI at the level of statistical reasoning.
2008	Zieffler, Garfield, Delmas and Reading	Inferential Reasoning It is to establish a framework necessary to support research on informal inferential reasoning (IIR). This framework is a comprehensive, researcher-focused framework that examines complex cognitive processes in detail, primarily to analyse students' processes of making informal inferences.	They addressed the ambiguity surrounding the meanings of the terms ISI and IIR, analysed their meanings, and provided clear definitions. They also defined the IIR process within a systematic research framework.
2009	Makar and Rubin	It is to provide a framework for informal inference. The Makar and Rubin framework has presented a simplified and applicable model, particularly in the context of teaching, by clearly defining its three components (Evidence from Data, Generalization Beyond Data, Probabilistic Language).	They have presented a widely used, three-component operational framework for analysing ISI.

Makar and Rubin's (2009) Informal Statistical Inference Framework

The main objective of Makar and Rubin's (2009) work is to propose a theoretical framework for statistical learning that uses non-formal inference as a process of meaning construction and evidence building, based on previous research on inferential statistical reasoning. This framework is a theoretical framework that uses non-formal inference as a process of meaning-making and evidence-building.

ISI can be summarised as a process in which a claim about a population or underlying process is made based on sample data and supported by a logic that embraces uncertainty. This process is not tied to formal concepts such as p-values, confidence intervals, or standard errors; instead, it requires students to reason about data, context, and variability prior to formal statistics instruction. There are three key components that define ISI within its framework:

1. Generalization Beyond Data: It involves making a claim that goes beyond specific data (i.e., making a claim about a population based on a sample or about a general process based on observed data, and this action is not about drawing conclusions based on what the data tells us).

A defining feature of inference is the act of generalization; moving from what is observed in a sample to statements about a broader group or process. In the classroom, this might mean moving from data about a group of students to claims about all students in a school, or from a series of coin toss results to claims about whether a coin is fair. Makar and Rubin emphasize that this generalization is not an automatic or obvious step for students. Engaging with ISI requires conscious reflection on what the data represents, such as its limitations and how these relate to the target population or process. This process sets the stage for misunderstandings (e.g., making predictions based on what is known or failing to consider sampling bias), making it the focal point of the teaching framework.

2. Evidence from Data: Using observed data to support or refute a specific claim (the process of using numerical, observation-based, or verbal data obtained during the inference process to accept or reject hypotheses presented at the generalization stage).

Within the ISI framework, data are not simple numbers to be manipulated, but rather the fundamental source of evidence for any claim. The process of making an inference requires not only stating what the data say, but also creating evidence that shows why these data support (or do not support) your generalization. Here, Makar and Rubin draw on the tradition of scientific evidence to frame statistical reasoning in the classroom in a manner similar to constructing and defending claims in science. This orientation reflects the tradition of “data as evidence” in statistics education, encouraging students to treat data as meaningful, context-rich elements at the centre of reasoning processes.

3. Probabilistic Language: Accepting and communicating that a claim is not certain and is subject to error or variability (this is very important for ISI, as it is based on the concepts of uncertainty and variability).

Perhaps the most challenging aspect of ISI for students is recognizing and communicating uncertainty. In formal statistics, this is encoded through confidence intervals, significance levels, and similar tools. In ISI, students must understand that claims about populations or processes based on sample data are never certain and that various forms of error, bias, or variability can intervene. Recognizing uncertainty is crucial both for the development of knowledge and for practical statistical thinking.

Makar and Rubin (2009) emphasize that ISI is not a one-time process but an iterative cycle. Students generate claims, compare them with data, revise or refine their reasoning, and reflect on the broader process. Through classroom-based experimental studies, they have observed how students' reasoning develops as they engage in these cycles, becoming increasingly adept at using evidence and recognizing uncertainty.

The researchers' frameworks make several important distinctions: The first is the distinction between formal and informal. ISI occurs before formal procedures and is not a “pre-

inference”; it is a genuine inference, albeit informal. The second is context sensitivity. ISI is based on real, contextual scenarios, not abstract textbook problems. That is, it treats statistical inference not as a mechanical process involving only numbers, but as a process that gains meaning within a specific problem context, refers to real-world events, and serves the purpose of explaining these events or making predictions about the future. The third is strong communication. The framework has a strong communication dimension that requires students not only to make statistical inferences but also to express these inferences clearly, support them with data, and explain the uncertainty they contain in an appropriate language. Evidence, explanation, and justification are central and reflect the social, discursive nature of inference in the real world.

The components within this framework, which seek to explain the mental processes individuals go through and the elements they focus on when making statistical inferences, can be considered as different levels or stages of informal statistical inference. Each component of the framework reflects the different levels at which individuals think and make decisions when making informal statistical inferences. In other words, these can be thought of as paths taken or stages of development in the inference process. From this perspective, Makar and Rubin's three-component framework provides a functional structure for understanding, teaching, and examining non-formal statistical inference, and, as in this study, each component represents a different level or dimension of the inference process.

Teacher Competence and the Situation in Turkey

Teachers are the most critical determinant of any educational reform and student achievement, and they can make a significant difference through their actions within the system. Ineffective teachers lead to adverse outcomes in students' academic achievement, regardless of how effective the school and/or curriculum may be. Among all school-related variables, teacher quality is considered the most potent factor affecting student academic achievement (Hattie, 2009).

Burrill and Biehler (2011) noted that statistics are often taught by mathematics teachers who have not received specialised training in statistics themselves, and therefore have insufficient knowledge of statistics; most lack experience in analysis, and do not understand the role of “uncertainty and variability.” They emphasised that this lack of competence in statistics education leads to the development of negative attitudes and beliefs among teachers, who may then neglect probabilistic thinking and weaken statistical understanding by teaching with traditional, procedural approaches that use examples that are disconnected from the real world or artificial.

In this context, mathematics teachers' knowledge of statistics and their pedagogical knowledge, which is the ability to transfer this knowledge to their students, is a critical condition for students to gain proficiency in vital subjects such as statistical reasoning. In other words, teaching students modern statistical literacy directly requires the presence of subject matter expert teachers who possess these skills. A teacher who lacks sufficient Statistical Content Knowledge (SCK) cannot be expected to impart complex reasoning skills, such as ISI.

This requirement has reached its peak in Turkey with the new Mathematics Course Curriculum implemented by the Ministry of National Education (MEB) in 2024. Apart from the significant problems brought about by the radical changes in teaching programs within a short period of time in the National Education system, the new teaching program shows a decrease in the number of learning outcomes in the probability and statistics field, mostly related to the use of ISI, for the first eight years, while the significant increase in the time allocated is noteworthy (Kale, 2024). Thus, the responsibility for imparting ISI skills to students has been placed on mathematics teachers. With this structural change, examining the ISI and

SCK levels at the core of the probability and statistics curriculum for mathematics teachers entails analysing an essential factor affecting students' success in this area.

State of the Literature and Research Gap

Batanero et al. (2011) stated that mathematics teachers at all levels have significant deficiencies in their SCK, as consistently supported in the literature. Due to these deficiencies, teachers are unable to move away from procedural understanding in statistics teaching and cannot create learning environments centered on conceptual understanding and based on key ideas such as inference, variability, and representation (Özmen et al., 2023; Gonzalez, 2014). Therefore, as mentioned earlier, it is considered unlikely that mathematics teachers can equip their students with complex reasoning skills such as informal statistical reasoning (ISR).

Although there is significant literature on students' NIF levels from an early age (Paparistodemou and Meletiou-Mavrotheris (2008), Leavy (2010), Makar, Bakker, and Ben-Zvi (2011), Pfannkuch (2011), Makar (2013), Garfield et al. (2015), Vetten et al. (2018)), studies on mathematics teachers' own ISI levels are quite limited. In general, the studies emphasize that statistical literacy and ISI are of central importance and that ISI skills acquired at an early age can significantly contribute to the learning of statistical concepts in later years. Furthermore, it has been noted that teachers' lack of statistical knowledge and training is a serious problem and that this lack of knowledge can lead to teachers' negative attitudes and beliefs towards statistics, causing them to find statistics difficult or incomprehensible.

In this context, although there is evidence of the positive impact of technology-supported inferential activities on students (Selçuk, 2016), very little is known about the extent to which and how mathematics teachers respond to statistical data in the context of ISI. In other words, the relationship between mathematics teachers' statistical domain knowledge and their ability to facilitate ISI in classroom settings has not been sufficiently researched. Considering that effective teaching generally requires a nuanced blend of subject expertise and awareness of ISI processes, understanding how these dimensions interact in the ISI context is critically important.

The Purpose of the Study

This study aims to thoroughly examine the levels of informal statistical reasoning (ISR) among middle school mathematics teachers in light of the theoretical framework components identified by Makar and Rubin (2009) and to fill the aforementioned research gap by revealing in detail the relationship between these skills and teachers' levels of statistical domain knowledge (SDK). To this end, answers were sought to the following questions:

What are the informal statistical inference skill levels of middle school mathematics teachers?

What are the Statistics content knowledge levels of middle school mathematics teachers?

Is there a relationship between the informal statistical inference and Statistics content knowledge levels of middle school mathematics teachers?

Is there a relationship between the professional working hours of middle school mathematics teachers and the informal statistical inference skill level?

Is there a relationship between the professional working hours of middle school mathematics teachers and the Statistics content knowledge level?

METHOD

Research Method

This study, which aims to examine the informal statistical inference skills and statistical knowledge levels of middle school mathematics teachers, employed a qualitative case study

design to examine the informal statistical inference skills and statistical knowledge of each member of a group of middle school mathematics teachers. A case study aims to examine an event, occurrence, or process in depth and imposes limitations on the scope of the study. The aim of case studies is not to make statistical generalisations about a population but to describe and understand the situation in detail (Creswell, 2013). The case in this research is to understand and describe teachers' informal statistical inference competencies, their levels of statistical domain knowledge, and the relationship between the two. A multiple case study design was used in order to examine and compare multiple cases.

Sample

The research group was selected using the purposive sampling method. When determining the participants, easily accessible case sampling and criterion sampling from the purposive sampling methods were used. The basic principle of the criterion sampling approach is to examine all situations that meet a set of predetermined criteria. These criteria can be determined by the researcher or a previously prepared list of criteria can be used (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013). The study group was formed with mathematics teachers working in middle schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education in the central districts of Mersin. The study group comprises 48 primary school mathematics teachers working in 18 middle schools. The criteria used in criterion sampling are the teachers' professional experience, educational status, and willingness to participate in the research. In the educational status criterion, attention was paid to the fact that the teachers had not changed their field and had not obtained the right to teach with a pedagogical formation education. In terms of seniority, attention was paid to selecting teacher groups with different working years. When referring to the participants, the pseudonyms T1, T2, T3,.....T48 were used for confidentiality and convenience (Table 2).

Table 2

Information on participants

Professional Working Time	Participants	f
Less than 10 years	T14, T16, T26, T30, T40, T44, T48	7
10-15 years	T1, T3, T7, T8, T12, T18, T23, T24, T25, T29, T31, T32, T36, T37, T39, T42, T43, T45, T46	19
16-20 years	T2, T4, T6, T10, T11, T17, T20, T22, T27, Ö28, T33, T34, T35, T38, T41	15
More than 20 years	T5, T9, T13, T15, T19, T21, T47	7

Data Collection Tools

This section includes the data collection tools used in the study and the details of their creation and development processes. Table 3 shows the data collection tools and their intended uses.

Table 3

Data collection tools and their intended uses

Data Collection Tool	Purpose of Use
Informal Statistical Inference Test (ISIT)	Examining the informal statistical inference levels of middle school mathematics teachers
Statistical Content Knowledge Test (SCKT)	Examining middle school mathematics teachers' content knowledge regarding statistics

The ISIT used as a data collection tool was developed based on the theoretical framework determined by Makar and Rubin (2009), which focuses on evidence from data, generalisation beyond data, and probabilistic language components. The SCKT was designed to measure not only teachers' ability to select, use, and operate accurately in central tendency

and dispersion measures but also their ability to interpret these measures and understand the relationships between them.

Pilot Study: First, a 24-question informal statistical inference test, most of which were previously used in the literature and some of which were taken from the textbooks taught in public schools in Turkey, and a 14-question SCK test was prepared by arranging them after receiving expert opinion. During the pilot study and subsequent stages, some difficulties were experienced in reaching teachers who would volunteer to participate in the study. Some of the teachers did not want to participate in the study because they thought that solving the questions would take a long time. On the other hand, some teachers clearly stated that they would not be able to solve the questions because they thought their statistical knowledge was limited to the Statistics course in their undergraduate studies. As a result, the informal statistical inference test and the SCK test were first applied to six middle school mathematics teachers under the researcher's supervision. During the application, explanations were given to the participants for questions that could not be understood without any guidance. After the tests were applied, the teachers' answers were examined in detail together by the researcher and an expert. The answers given to the questions, regardless of whether they were correct or incorrect, were evaluated only in terms of whether the figures or graphs in the questions, the wording of the questions were understood, and the time allocated to answer the questions. Questions that were not fully understood or were similar to each other were identified. Some teachers stated that they left answers blank because the graphics were not understandable or the expressions were unclear. Since it was observed in the pilot study that teachers needed much time to answer the questions in detail, the number of questions was reduced by using one of the similar questions that was easily understood by most participants.

Data Collection Process

After the tests were finalised, the basic data collection process of the study was planned, and the informal statistical inference test and statistical field knowledge test were applied to 48 middle school mathematics teachers. Both tests were applied in a single session in the schools where the participants worked and under the researcher's supervision. Since the participants worked in different schools, the test was applied to the teachers or groups of teachers working in each school at different times. Interaction between the teachers was prevented during the application of the tests, and they were allowed to give individual answers to the questions. In addition, after examining the questions of the informal statistical inference test, which was the first test, the researcher made an explanation in order to reduce the level of anxiety that some participants said, "I would be embarrassed if I answered the questions wrong" and explained that the statements to be used in the answers would not be evaluated according to whether the answers were right or wrong, but according to the theoretical framework.

Data Analysis

During the informal statistical inference test analysis, the statements corresponding to each component of the theoretical framework were associated with predetermined codes. The participants' answers were examined in detail according to these codes. The answers to the SCK test questions were analysed for content. A scoring table based on expert opinion was created, and separate scores were given for each answer. Content analysis aims to connect certain concepts and topics by identifying similar data, organising it, and interpreting it in a structure that the reader can understand (Creswell, 2013).

Analysis of Informal Statistical Inference Test (ISIT)

During the analysis process, the focus was not on the correctness or incorrectness of the answers given by the teachers; instead, the extent to which these answers were compatible with

the components determined by the theoretical framework was examined. For each question, codes were determined in advance to reflect the theoretical framework and the teachers' answers were evaluated in detail in line with these codes. With this method, the data obtained from the informal statistical inference test were analysed in depth to understand mathematics teachers' informal statistical inference skills and theoretical understanding by focusing on each component. The same theoretical framework was also used in a study conducted by Selçuk (2016) on 9th-grade students, and in this context, the following statements corresponding to the components were determined.

Table 4

Statements corresponding to the components of the theoretical framework sought in the data (Selçuk, 2016).

Evidence from Data	Generalizing Beyond Data	Probabilistic Language
-Inference is expressed with expressions such as “according to” or “for”.	Going beyond the data, a claim is made for the population, and it is stated that this is valid for the entire population.	- The sentence is completed with subjective and uncertain expressions such as "Maybe?", "Could it be?" or "I think so?" or it begins the sentence with a subjective (in my opinion) expression.
- The information for which the data is used is clearly and unambiguously stated		- Expressions such as "definitely" are not used in a sentence.-
- As "can be seen", the expression draws attention to a specific place.		-Uncertainty is expressed properly.

The answer to each question in the informal statistical inference test was evaluated as "sufficient" or "insufficient" depending on whether it contained the appropriate expression in the table according to the theoretical framework component to which it was related.

Analysis of Statistics Content Knowledge Test (SCKT)

For a detailed analysis of the data obtained from SCK, the answers given by the teachers were examined in detail by the researcher, and an expert and content analysis was performed. In this process, appropriate answer patterns were created for each question, a scoring scale based on these patterns was prepared, and the analysis process was completed. When the questions were examined on a scale basis, if the wrong central tendency or dispersion measure was used for each question, it was evaluated as low level (0 points). If the answer was correct but there were deficiencies in the explanations, it was evaluated as medium level (1 or 2 points), and if the answer was written entirely with the explanation, it was evaluated as high level (3 points).

Table 5
Rating scale of the SCK test

	3 point	2 point	1 point	0 point
Question 1	Pays attention to extreme values, uses arithmetic mean and explains correctly.	Pays attention to extreme values, uses arithmetic mean but gives two answers or misinterprets 0.	It uses the arithmetic mean but ignores outliers.	Use measures of central tendency and dispersion in context.
Question 2	Explains the changes in mean and standard deviation accurately and adequately.	It correctly describes the standard deviation and change in the mean, but the explanation is inadequate.	Correctly states and explains only one of the changes in the standard deviation and mean.	Uses an incorrect statement about the mean or standard deviation. Uses general statements about the standard deviation and arithmetic mean, but does not say exactly how the change will occur.
Question 3	It states the measure of central tendency correctly and provides a complete explanation.	It gives the correct measure of central tendency but leaves the explanation incomplete.	The measure of central tendency is said correctly but cannot be explained/is done incorrectly.	It gives the wrong measure of central tendency.
Question 4	Provides complete calculations and explanations of the correct measure of central tendency.	It calculates the measure of central tendency correctly, but there are gaps in the explanation.	Makes a general comment about measures of central tendency/ Calculates the measure of central tendency incorrectly but makes a correct comment	Compares individual data instead of using a measure of central tendency/Cannot make any interpretation/Uses the wrong measure of central tendency.
Question 5	Says and draws the appropriate graph.	Says the appropriate graph but makes errors in drawing.	It says the appropriate graph is incorrect, but the graph drawing is correct.	Cannot say or draw appropriate graph.

FINDINGS

Findings of Informal Statistical Inference Test (ISIT)

When the answers to the ISI test, which was first applied to middle school mathematics teachers in the study to examine their informal statistical inference skills, were analysed, the sufficient and insufficient response rates are shown in Table 5.

Table 6

Distribution of answers in the ISIT according to whether they are sufficient or insufficient according to the theoretical framework components.

Informal statistical inference level	Evidence from data	Generalising beyond data	Probabilistic language
Sufficient	47 person (~%98)	40 person (~%83)	28 person (~%58)
Insufficient	1 person (~%2)	8 person (~%17)	20 person (~%42)

According to the table, the theoretical framework component that teachers use most in their answers is evidence from data with approximately 98%, followed by generalisation beyond data with approximately 83%. The component with the lowest rate of adequate answers was determined as probabilistic language. Examples of answers evaluated as adequate and inadequate in the context of all three components are given below.

An example of an adequate response in the context of the generalisation beyond the data component:

“The question does not state how many minutes before Osman leaves home for class. If we assume that he leaves 20 minutes before class, I would prefer the highway because the waiting time of the car in the parking lot will be shorter.”

In the answer above, the data was carefully reviewed, and the participant generalised, together with his own prediction, that the waiting time would decrease when the main road was used. This statement is an evaluation based on the data and can be considered a very appropriate answer in the context of the generalisation beyond the data component.

Insufficient answer example in the context of generalisation beyond the data:

“I would choose the freeway. When I averaged the data over five days, I decided the freeway made more sense.”

In this answer, another participant's inadequate answer in terms of generalisation beyond the data is seen. The average of the data was calculated, but the answer was given without any comment or generalisation.

Example of adequate response in the context of evidence component from data:

“3, 4, 4, 4 Arithmetic mean and median are equal. Idil. Because the peak value is higher. 3, 3, 4, 5 “

In this answer, it is seen that the evidence component from the data is clearly used, as the participant writes the data in order from smallest to largest, calculates the median value and arithmetic mean, and gives an answer based on this.

Example of an insufficient response for the evidence component from the data:

“I think Idil should be sent away. ”

In this answer, where the use of the evidence component is expected, the participant only wrote the name he thought was the correct answer without basing it on data and without writing any explanation. Therefore, the answer was considered insufficient.

A sufficient answer example regarding the use of the probabilistic language component:

“Mode, median, and range affect the probabilities. I think the reason for the anomalous results in the randomly selected sample is because the sample size is larger than the small school.”
The above answer was accepted as a sufficient answer within the scope of the probabilistic language component because it included a subjective expression used by the participant, such as “...I think it is.”

An example of an inadequate answer regarding the use of the probabilistic language component:

“It is due to those selected from small schools. Because even one person selected from a small number of people has a high rate of affecting the rate. $1/20 > 1/50$ $1/20$ has a higher effect.”

This answer was evaluated as an insufficient answer in the context of the probabilistic language component because it contained definite expressions such as “it is due to, it is more than” instead of a sentence containing a subjective expression or a prediction meaning.

The distribution of teachers according to the number of components that can be used is shown in the table below.

Table 7

Distribution of adequate answers in the ISIT according to theoretical framework components.

Number of Teachers	Evidence from Data	Generalising Beyond Data	Probabilistic Language
25 person (approximately %52)	✓	✓	✓
15 person (approximately %31)	✓	✓	
2 person (approximately %4)	✓		✓
5 person (approximately %10)	✓		
1 person (approximately %2)			✓

Table 6 shows the distribution of teachers' competence in using theoretical framework components in their responses to the ISIT according to the theoretical framework components. In this context, it was observed that only 25 of the teachers were able to successfully use all three components of the theoretical framework in their responses. Seventeen teachers were able to use any two of the three components, and the remaining six teachers were able to use only one component. When a general evaluation is made in line with these findings, it is seen that the lowest rate among the components that teachers use at an adequate level belongs to the probabilistic language component.

Findings of the SCK Test

When the teachers' scores in the entire IAB test are examined, the lowest score that can be obtained is "0," and the highest score is "15." Four of the teachers have scores between 11 and 15 (high level), 28 have scores between 5 and 10 (medium level), and 16 have scores between 0 and 4 (low level). Examples of answers with low, medium, and high scores for some questions in the test are given below.

Answer from a teacher with low-level SCK (0 points):

"By looking at the peak values."

In this question, teachers were asked to choose the most appropriate measure of central tendency or dispersion to be used to compare data groups, but the answer given was incorrect and was evaluated as low level.

Teacher with intermediate level (1 or 2 points) SCK answer:

"The median should be used to avoid being affected by extreme values."

In the question above, the participant wrote the central tendency measure that best represents the data group correctly, but since he could not explain it, this answer was accepted as medium level.

Teacher with high level (3 points) SCK answer:

"The arithmetic mean increases when an outlier is removed. The standard deviation decreases. If a value below the mean is removed from the data, the arithmetic mean increases. When the outlier value of 4 is removed, the data deviates less from the mean. Therefore, the standard deviation decreases."

In this answer, which is accepted as high level, the change in arithmetic mean and standard deviation is expressed correctly, and appropriate explanations are made for both. The level distributions of the evaluation made on a question basis based on the answers of 48 mathematics teachers who participated in the IAB test are clearly seen in the graph shown in

Figure. This graph allows us to understand the evaluation results by visually presenting the different levels of statistical knowledge of teachers.

Figure 1. Level distribution of teachers according to their scores on the questions in the SCK Test.

Figure 2. Level distribution of teachers according to their overall scores from all questions in the SCK Test

Findings for the Evaluation of the Relationship Between the Informal Statistical Inference Test and Statistical Field Knowledge Test Results

In the ISIT, 25 teachers could successfully use all three components of the theoretical framework, 17 teachers could use two components, and six teachers could only use one component. Of the 25 teachers who could use three components, only 4 had high-level statistics knowledge. Fourteen had intermediate level, and the remaining 7 had low-level statistics knowledge. Among the 17 teachers who could use two components, no one had high-level statistics knowledge. There were 9 teachers at the intermediate level and eight at the low level. Among the six teachers who could use only one of the components, there was no teacher with high-level content knowledge. There were four teachers at the intermediate level and 2 at the low level.

Findings on the Relationship Between Length of Professional Experience and ISIT and SCKT

It has been determined that teachers' working years are mostly concentrated between 10 and 15 years, and there are a total of 19 teachers in this period. This section will present the findings on the relationship between teachers' informal statistical inference skills and their professional experience.

A total of 25 teachers were identified who could effectively use the three basic components of the theoretical framework. Among these teachers, the largest group consisted of

teachers with 10-15 years of professional experience. The lowest rate was among teachers with more than 20 years of professional experience. Among the 17 teachers who could use only two components of the theoretical framework, the highest density was among those with 16-20 years of experience and the lowest density was observed in those with less than 10 years of professional experience. Among the six teachers who could effectively use only one component, the highest density was among teachers with 10-15 years of experience. Among the 16 teachers with 16-20 years of professional experience, there was no teacher who could use a single component. The findings show that the professional experience periods of teachers who could use the components the most and the least were concentrated in the same ranges. Table 8 is provided for easier understanding of the findings.

Table 8

Number of teachers who can use the components of the theoretical framework according to their professional experience.

	Providing3 components	Providing2 components	Providing1 components
Less than 10 Years	4	2	1
10-15 Years	11	4	3
16-20 Years	9	7	none
More Than 20 Years	1	4	2
Total	25	17	6

According to the findings of the SCKT, 3 out of 4 teachers with high level of field knowledge have 10-15 years of professional experience, and 1 has 16-20 years of professional experience. When the distribution of 27 teachers with a medium level of SCK is examined, 13 have 10-15 years of professional experience, 8 have 16-20 years of professional experience, 3 have more than 20 years of professional experience, and 3 have less than 10 years of professional experience. Among the 17 teachers with low levels of SCK, 6 have 16-20 years of professional experience, 4 have less than 10 years of professional experience, 3 have 10-15 years of professional experience, and the remaining 4 have more than 20 years of professional experience. Table 9 has been added for easier reading of this information.

Table 9

Number of teachers with statistical field knowledge levels according to their professional experience.

	High-Level SCK	Intermediate Level SCK	Low-Level SCK
Less than 10 Years	none	3	4
10-15 Years	3	13	3
16-20 Years	1	8	6
More than 20 Years	none	3	4

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Teachers, who are among the primary factors shaping mathematics instruction, must first possess comprehensive subject matter knowledge to teach the content. Teachers who have deficiencies or mistakes in field knowledge may convey these mistakes to students may fail to correct students' conceptual errors, and may not be able to conduct the lesson in a student-centred manner (Käpylä, Heikkinen, & Asunta, 2009). In this context, it would not be wrong to say that it is essential for teachers to have sufficient field knowledge in order to be productive in teaching probability and statistics since they have an important place in students' daily life skills.

In this study, contrary to the literature, teachers' informal statistical inference skill levels were examined instead of teacher candidates and students at all levels and their relationship with their statistical field knowledge was discussed. After a detailed analysis of the teachers' answers, it was determined in the results obtained that the evidence from the data component was used the most, followed by the generalisation beyond the data component. However, it was observed that the teachers' skills in using the probabilistic language component were not as developed as the other two components. As stated in the findings section, 47 out of 48 teachers could use the evidence from the data component, 40 were able to use the generalisation beyond the data component, and 28 could use the probabilistic language component. Based on these data, it is possible to say that the component in which teachers are weakest in using the theoretical framework components is probabilistic language, which is quite important for informal statistical inference. When a general evaluation is made within the scope of the theoretical framework, it is thought that teachers' skills in making Informal statistical inferences are lower than expected. As mentioned before, since informal statistical inference skills are increasingly important in every area of life, schools stand out as one of the most important places where these skills can be effectively developed. Therefore, it is expected that teachers who provide education to individuals are well-equipped in their fields and demonstrate inference skills by mastering all three components of the theoretical framework. However, the results obtained in this study indicate that most of the teachers have insufficient Informal statistical inference skills, especially in the context of the probabilistic language component, and that each teacher does not have sufficient skills in other components. This is because teachers focus on data-based calculations when answering questions and feel the need to use definite expressions after these calculations. Therefore, expressions belonging to the probabilistic language component were encountered at a low rate in the answers. It is thought that this situation is caused by the fact that the statistics courses that mathematics teachers take during their undergraduate education are generally based on calculations and that they tend to teach statistical knowledge and skills to students in a calculation- and exam-oriented manner after the undergraduate process. The fact that the purpose of mathematics education, especially at the middle and high school levels in Turkey, is oriented toward exams students will take as a result of these educational processes, and that the questions in these exams are multiple-choice and based on operations and calculations, also supports this idea.

When the teachers' SCK is examined, it is seen that the SCKT answers are generally concentrated at a medium level. Despite the correct answers, the answers that are incomplete, vague or provide limited explanations are evaluated at a medium level. In some questions, the number of teachers who can answer in the high-level SCK category is quite limited. Only 4 out of 48 mathematics teachers have a high-level SCK, which is a very low rate. The findings revealed that teachers generally have difficulty in questions requiring high-level field knowledge in the SCKT and show deficiencies in this regard. While the mathematics teachers who participated in the study could give sufficient answers to questions that had a small number of data or included a single data group, they gave insufficient answers to questions that included more than one data group and were based on the comparison. These inadequacies stemmed from their inability to use correct central tendency measures, especially when comparing data groups. The main reason for this situation is that teachers tend to use only their computational skills when comparing data groups and are inadequate in making inferences.

The results are similar to previous studies and are consistent with the findings of studies on students' Informal Statistical Inference skills (Ben-Zvi, 2006; Paparistodemou and Meletio-Mavrotheris, 2008; Selçuk, 2016; Öztürk, 2019). The general trend in the literature is that although students generally use the components related to evidence from the data effectively in data analysis, they have difficulty generalising beyond the data, especially in components that include probabilistic language. There are emphases that students have difficulty understanding

and using probabilistic language in particular. Similarly, this study points to similar trends by evaluating teachers' informal statistical inference skill levels in parallel with previous student-focused studies. The study is based on the findings of studies conducted on students, and these findings emphasise the importance of evaluating teachers' informal statistical inference skills because teachers have a key role in teaching statistics, as in every field.

When the relationship between teachers' informal statistical inference skills and SCK is examined, it is concluded that in order to have strong inference skills and make informal statistical inferences, their level of SCK must be high. Among the teachers, those with a high level of SCK can use SCK based on interpretation and inference. Those with a low level of SCK are those who have difficulty understanding the relationships between data, cannot decide on the appropriate central tendency measure, and give answers focused only on calculation.

The teachers who can use all three components of the theoretical framework are mostly those with 10-15 years of professional experience. The fact that teachers with less than 10 years of experience consider the statistical knowledge they acquired during their undergraduate studies only through a calculation-based approach may mean that the teachers in this group understand statistical concepts only through their calculation skills. In addition, the limited experience of the teachers in this group may suggest that their knowledge in this field is incomplete. On the other hand, it is thought that teachers with more than 20 years of experience may have insufficient professional excitement and desire to learn due to reasons such as economic difficulties they experience in their country and unfavourable working conditions, and they may not have developed interpretation and inference skills, which have more weight in gains over time. This situation may indicate that long-term professional experience may reduce learning flexibility and that, after a certain point, teachers are limited in being open to innovations. Most teachers with high- and medium-level SCK have 10 to 15 years of professional experience, as shown in the findings regarding informal statistical inference skills. The reasons mentioned above can be listed as the main reasons for this situation. In addition, while this period can be considered an ideal period for teachers to gain experience, it is also an early period for professional fatigue to occur. This situation has increased the teachers' curiosity to acquire new information by preserving the field knowledge they acquired during their undergraduate studies, and at the same time, it has allowed them to continue their efforts to update and develop their knowledge.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study determined that teachers struggled with the topics of 'Generalisation Beyond Data' and, in particular, 'Probabilistic Language'. Therefore, it is necessary to modernise the in-service training programmes organised by the Ministry of National Education (MEB) and to restructure them to include scenario-based ISI activities rather than formula-based ones. In addition, a teacher handbook containing data-based inference techniques should be prepared to guide teachers on the statistical learning outcomes in the 2024 mathematics teaching programme.

In preparing pre-service teachers for the profession, it is recommended that microteaching applications that develop pre-service teachers' informal statistical inference skills be emphasised in Statistics and Probability teaching courses at Faculties of Education.

This study presents a snapshot of the current situation of mathematics teachers. Future studies could examine the long-term impact of teacher training for teachers and/or teacher candidates. Furthermore, the relationship between SCK and ISI could be statistically modelled using quantitative scales with a large sample size representative of Turkey as a whole, and the contributions of dynamic statistical software to teachers' ISI processes could be investigated.

It is thought that similar results would be obtained if a study similar to this one, conducted in Turkey, were carried out in countries with similar economic conditions to Turkey.

However, it would be interesting to examine the seniority landscape in other countries with higher economic levels; researchers conducting such a study could address this curiosity.

During data collection for this study, many teachers declined to participate due to negative attitudes and concerns about statistics. Studies could be conducted to determine whether this situation is also valid in other countries. As stated by Batur et al. (2021), studies could be conducted to determine the levels of attitudes and concerns toward statistics in countries that include statistics achievements at different levels in their mathematics teaching programmes.

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APPENDICES**A-1. INFORMAL STATISTICAL INFERENCE TEST (ISIT)**

Question 1: Osman will go to summer school for 10 weeks in the summer. His school is 10 km away from Osman's house. Osman has two different routes to choose from to get to school: the ring road and the main road. The ring road is shorter, but there are more traffic lights on the ring road. The main road is longer, but there are fewer traffic lights on this road. In order to decide which of the two roads to choose, he conducted experiments using two different roads and found out how many minutes it took to get to school, as shown in the table.

Highway	17	15	17	16	18
Ring road	18	13	20	10	16

Osman wants to get to school on time, but he doesn't want to go too early because he doesn't want to pay extra parking fees. According to the table, which route would you recommend Osman to choose? Explain with reasons (Garfield et al., 2002; Garfield and delMas, 2010).

Question 2: The researchers went to two different schools, one small and one large. The number of girls and boys in each school was approximately equal. The researchers took random samples from each school as follows:

- 50 students from the large school
- 20 students from the small school

These samples yielded an anomalous result of more than 80% boys. Do you think this result is most likely from the 50-student sample from the large school or the 20-student sample from the small school? Or is this sample equally likely to come from either school? Explain why (Watson et al, 2000).

Question 3:

MATHEMATICS NETS															
FEMALE	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6	G7	G8	G9	G10	G11	G12	G13	G14	G15
	3	4	11	10,5	13	8,5	7	13	13	10	8	9	5	14	12
MALE	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15
	4	6	7,5	11	12	8	8,5	10	10	7	9	11	10	17	10

Table: The net scores of male and female students in the 8th grade of a school in Mathematics in a mock exam.

- How do you compare the scores of male and female students according to the table?
- Which group of students would you say will be more successful in mathematics in the high school entrance exam they will take at the end of the term? Explain your reasoning in detail. (This question was created by the researcher after receiving an expert opinion.)

Question 4:

Table: İdil and Kıvanç's written grades in Mathematics

İdil	4	3	4	4	5
Kıvanç	5	4	3	3	5

The table above shows the written grades of two students, İdil and Kıvanç, from a mathematics course throughout the year. Decide which of these students would be more appropriate to send to a knowledge contest. Explain your reasoning (MoNE 2018, p.347).

Question 5: Mr. Harun is the Izmir dealer of an automobile company. This company has a monthly sales target. Mr. Harun decides to hire a salesperson to achieve the monthly target. The table below shows the central tendency and dispersion measures of the number of cars sold by the two candidates in the last ten months.

	Mean	Median	Mode	Range
Oğuz	8,6	9	6	5
Sercan	7,9	6	5	15

Accordingly;

- Which salesperson should Harun prefer in a month when he has 9 cars to sell? Explain why.
- Which salesperson should Harun prefer when he has 14 cars to sell? Explain why (MoNE, 2016)

A-2. STATISTICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE TEST (SCKT)

Question 1: A teacher wants to change the seating arrangement in her classroom in the hope that this will increase the number of students who attend class. She first decides to look at how many times a week students attend class with the current seating arrangement. The total number of times eight students attend class during a week is recorded and is shown below.

The first letter of students' names	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Number of class participants	0	5	2	22	3	2	1	2

The data is to be summarised by examining the number of students who participated in the lesson for that week. Which of the following methods would you recommend the teacher use? Explain your reasoning (Garfield, 2003, p.34)

- Use the most common number, 2
- Add 8 numbers and divide by 8
- Drop 22, add the other 7 numbers and divide by 7
- Drop 0, add the other 7 numbers and divide by 7
- Drop 0 and 22, calculate the average for 6 people

Question 2: A random sample of 30 freshmen at a university was selected to estimate the mean score on a math placement test for all freshmen. The mean for the sample was found to be 81.7, and the standard deviation was found to be 11.45. An outlier with a placement score of 4 was found in this data set. How would the mean and standard deviation be affected if this outlier were removed? Why would removing the outlier have this effect on the mean and standard deviation? Explain (Garfield et al., 2010)

Question 3: The number of music players sold by a store selling electronic products in the last nine days is as follows.

23, 19, 23, 1, 20, 21, 23, 20, 21

Accordingly, which central tendency measure best represents the number of music players sold? Explain (MoNE, 2018, p.348)

Question 4 and 5:

Answer questions 4 and 5 according to the table below.

ABSENCES												
Female	16	20	5,5	10	11	14	3,5	5	8	16	16	8
Male	9,5	18	18	10	10	6	3	4,5	11	18	6	7

The data in the table shows the school absences of girls and boys in a class during a year.

Question 4: How do you compare the absences of girls and boys?

Question 5: Which graph would be appropriate to compare the absenteeism of male and female students? Draw the graph and explain why you chose this graph (Koparan and Güven, 2013).